
Research

Dynamics and Model Validation of High Speed Train Axle Box Bearings

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Abstract: With the rapid development of high-speed trains, the independent innovation of key parts of high-speed trains is an important support for the implementation of the "manufacturing power" and the "the Belt and Road" strategy. The axle box bearing is one of the key components of the high-speed train running gear, and once it malfunctions, it will seriously affect the safe operation of the train. During the actual operation of trains, it is difficult to directly observe the dynamic behavior of various components inside the bearings through sensors, and most bearings are in normal service, and bearing fault data is difficult to obtain. Therefore, conducting dynamic simulation of faults in high-speed train axle box bearings, simulating the fault information of bearings, analyzing the changes in stress and motion characteristics of faulty bearings, is of great significance for fault monitoring of axle box bearings.

Keywords: High-Speed trains; Axle box bearing; Fault; Dynamic simulation; Fault diagnosis

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Introduction

Compared with conventional trains, high-speed trains not only have higher speeds but also better ride comfort. This is because during the design and manufacturing process of high-speed trains, the parameters that affect their safety, smoothness, and stability indicators have been optimized. The excellent performance of high-speed trains also puts forward high requirements for the working performance of their internal components. The axle box device of high-speed trains is a key component that connects and moves between train wheel sets and frames, playing a connecting role in train operation.

The axle box bearing of high-speed trains is the most important component for transmitting motion and load in its axle box device. In order to reduce the resistance of train operation and in response to the large allowable axle load of railway vehicles, high-speed train axle box bearings mostly use cylindrical roller bearings and tapered roller bearings with larger bearing capacity. The bearings are mainly composed of four parts: inner ring, outer ring, rolling element, and cage; After the assembly of the bearings, lubricants need to be added to avoid direct metal contact between rolling elements and to prevent the invasion of debris. For high-speed train axle box bearings, sealing devices are simpler and maintenance is easier with lubricating grease as the lubricant.

Fig.1 Physical image of high-speed train axle box bearings

Axle box bearings can be divided into cylindrical roller bearings and tapered roller bearings based on their structural form and parameter selection. At present, the axle box bearings of various types of CRH high-speed trains in China are all imported, although they are not from the same manufacturer (CRH1 and CRH5 use SKF bearings; CRH2 uses NTN and NSK bearings; CRH3 uses FAG bearings), but they all adopt the structural form of double row tapered roller bearings. It is installed at both ends of the wheel hub and bears the complex loads generated between the wheel set and the bogie structure.

The overall dimensions of China's 200km grade bearings are $d \times D \times B = 130\text{mm} \times 230\text{mm} \times 160\text{mm}$; The overall dimensions of 300km level bearings are $d \times D \times B = 130\text{mm} \times 240\text{mm} \times 160\text{mm}$. In general, 16 rolling elements are used for each column, with a rolling element size of $30\text{mm} \times 48\text{mm}$.

Structural form and simulation related parameters of axle box bearings

The axle box bearings of high-speed trains are mainly divided into three types: double row round hammer roller bearings, double row cylindrical roller bearings, and self-aligning bearings.

Cylindrical roller bearing

Round hammer roller bearing

Fig. 2 Types of Axle Box Bearings

The axle box bearings of high-speed trains are mainly composed of outer rings, inner rings, cages, rolling elements, and other parts. Their main function is to bear the weight and load of the vehicle body and transmit it to the wheel set, as well as to achieve mutual movement between the wheel set and the frame. The outer ring is fixed to the bearing seat through an interference fit, and the inner ring is fixed to the axle through an interference fit. When the train is running, the outer ring is fixed to the bearing seat without rotation, while the inner ring rotates with the rotation of the axle. Due to the effect of friction, when the inner ring rotates, it causes the rolling element to roll between the inner and outer rings. The motion of the rolling element mainly consists of two parts: revolution around the central axis of the bearing and rotation around the central axis of the rolling element. When the rolling element undergoes revolution under the friction of the inner ring, it collides with the cage, causing the cage to rotate around the center of the bearing with the revolution of the rolling element. The cage also guides the movement of the rolling element.

The detailed parameters of the bearing structure are shown in Table 1. The bearing pitch diameter in the table refers to the diameter of the circle where the center of the roller is located, and the contact angle is the angle between the direction of the roller force and the vertical line of the inner and outer ring raceways.

Table 1 Structural parameters of high-speed train axle box bearings

Basic parameters of high-speed rail bearings	Value
Nominal inner diameter d	130 mm
Nominal outside diameter D	230 mm
Pitch Diameter D_{pw}	180.6 mm
Width B	160 mm
Number of single row rollers z	21
Roller big end diameter D_b	22.6 mm
Roller small end diameter D_s	22 mm
Roller length L	45.5 mm
Inner circle contact angle α_i	7.75 °
Outer ring contact angle α_o	10 °

The double row tapered roller bearing mainly bears radial load and can also bear axial load. Its inner ring is in an interference fit with the axle journal, and as the axle rotates, the outer ring is in a clearance fit with the axle box body, bearing the load through the axle box body. When high-speed trains operate normally, their speed can reach 350km/h, and their wheel diameter is generally 860mm. From this, it can be calculated that the inner ring speed of the axle box bearings of high-speed trains during normal operation is about 2160r/min.

Verification of Normal Bearing Dynamics Model

After creating the dynamic model of the axle box bearing, simulation analysis can be conducted to obtain information such as the angular velocity of the bearing rollers and cage. The simulation results can be compared with the theoretical calculation results to verify the rationality of the model. During simulation calculation, the angular velocity of the inner ring of the bearing is set to 180 rad/s, and the angular velocity of the outer ring is set to 0 rad/s. Based on the bearing parameters in Table 1 ,equations 1-1 and 1-2 the theoretical angular velocities of the roller and cage are -718.10 rad/s (negative sign indicates that the direction of rotation of the roller is opposite to the inner ring) and 79.06 rad/s, respectively. Compare the simulated cage and roller angular velocity with the theoretical calculation results, as shown in Figure 3.

a) Verification of cage angular velocity b) Roller angular velocity verification

Figure 3 Comparison between Theoretical and Simulation Values of Cage and Roller Angular Velocity

In the process of kinematic theoretical analysis of rolling bearings, in order to facilitate the analysis, the motion process of rolling bearings has been simplified to a certain extent: assuming that the motion of the bearings is uniform,

the influence of bearing lubrication is not considered, and the elastic-plastic deformation of various components of the bearings is not considered. Due to the fact that during the operation of rolling bearings, the angular velocity of the cage rotation is the same as the angular velocity of the roller centroid rotating around the center of the bearing, the angular velocity ω_c of the cage is:

$$\omega_c = \frac{1}{2} \omega_i \left(1 - \frac{D_w}{D_{pw}} \cos \alpha \right) + \frac{1}{2} \omega_e \left(1 + \frac{D_w}{D_{pw}} \cos \alpha \right) \tag{1-1}$$

In the equation: ω_c is the angular velocity of the cage (rad/s).

Therefore, the theoretical rotational speed of the roller can be obtained as:

$$\omega_r = \frac{1}{2} \frac{D_{pw}}{D_w} (\omega_i - \omega_e) \left[1 - \left(\frac{D_w}{D_{pw}} \cos \alpha \right)^2 \right] \tag{1-2}$$

In the equation: ω_r is the rotational speed of the roller (rad/s).

The simulated value of the angular velocity of the cage is about 80 rad/s, with an error of 1.19% compared to the theoretical calculation results; The simulated value of roller angular velocity is about 690 rad/s, and compared with the theoretical calculation results, the error is 3.91%. The comparison results are shown in Table 2. Considering that the rollers cannot continuously perform pure rolling during the operation of the bearings, as well as the simplification of the model during modeling, and the software itself has certain solving errors, the above error values are within a reasonable range, which can verify the rationality of the dynamic model of the axle box bearing.

Table 2 Comparison between Simulation Results and Theoretical Results of Roller and Cage

Bearing elements	Simulation value(rad/s)	Theoretical (rad/s)	Error(rad/s)
Holder	80	79.06	1.19
Roller	690	718.10	3.91

Verification of dynamic model for faulty bearings

After completing the creation of the dynamic model of the outer ring peeling fault bearing, simulation analysis is conducted on it. Based on the simulated angular velocity and acceleration data, the rationality of the outer ring fault bearing dynamic model is verified by comparing it with the theoretical calculation results. Under the condition of outer ring failure, the peeling fault is located on the raceway on the right side of the bearing outer ring. The angular velocity of the right cage and roller of the axle box bearing is shown in Figure 4. From Figure 4 (a), it can be seen that when the outer ring fails, the angular velocity of the cage fluctuates around 80 rad/s, similar to normal bearings, but with a greater amplitude of fluctuation. In Figure 4 (b), there is not much difference in the average angular velocity of the roller between the normal bearing and the faulty outer ring bearing. However, under the fault condition, the amplitude of the change in the angular velocity of the roller increases, and there is also a periodic mutation in the angular velocity of the roller.

The time interval for the mutation is 0.0785 seconds, with a frequency of 12.74 Hz, which is close to the simulated cage rotation frequency of 12.73 Hz. This is because the roller will collide once with the peeling fault on the outer ring raceway after one revolution, The sudden change in roller angular velocity occurs at the same frequency as the rotation

frequency of the cage, indicating that the common angular velocity of the roller is consistent with the angular velocity of the cage rotation, which is in line with the actual situation.

a) Right cage angular velocity

b) Right roller angular velocity

Figure 4 Angular velocity of cage and roller during outer ring failure

Conclusion

This paper provides a detailed introduction to the modeling process of dynamic models for normal and faulty axle box bearings. Firstly, geometric models of normal and faulty bearings were established based on the structural parameters of the bearings. Secondly, based on Hertz contact theory, the dynamic models of normal bearing, inner ring peeling fault, and outer ring peeling fault bearing were established considering three working conditions: the axle box bearing is in normal state, the bearing outer ring has peeling fault, and the inner ring has peeling fault.

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